

iCourts

iCourts Working Paper Series, no. 213, 2020

IMAGINE Paper No.

Why read *The Transformation of Europe* today? On the limits of a liberal constitutional imaginary

**Conference *EU Constitutional Imagination: Between Ideology and
Utopia***

Jan Komárek

iCourts – The Danish National Research Foundation's
Centre of Excellence for International Courts

September 2020

Abstract: This article argues that reading Transformation today may help us understand the limits of liberal constitutional imaginary, on which Transformation builds and which it helped to establish in the 1990s. Now, when ‘Western liberalism’ is on retreat, such critical reading may be indispensable for those who look for alternatives.

The article is structured as follows: Part 2 briefly defines the concept of ‘constitutional imaginary’. Part 3 provides a brief genealogy of Transformation and offers a critical reading of the whole essay, which prepares grounds for Part 4, where Transformation’s constitutional imaginary based on liberal-legalist ideology combined with a communitarian utopia is outlined. It is shown how each of them contradicts the other, but at the same time, how none can exist without the other. Part 5 reveals what Transformation (and its imaginary) hides from sight: how its rendering of European integration’s history, reduced to the narrative of Europe’s founding fathers’ reflective choice for Europe, and the ignorance of political economy, overlooks the complex and complicated histories of the states that came to form the Union. The conclusion finally connects these findings to the current issues facing the EU and liberal constitutionalism as such.

KEYWORDS: European constitutional imagination, Joseph Weiler, liberal constitutionalism, communitarian utopia

Jan Komárek, Professor of European law, *iCourts*, Faculty of Law, University of Copenhagen and Principal Investigator of IMAGINE (see below)

Email: Jan.Komarek@jur.ku.dk

IMAGINE has received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (grant agreement No 803163).

The iCourts Working Paper Series is funded by the Danish National Research Foundation Grant no. DNRF105.

iCourts - Centre of Excellence for International Courts - focuses on the ever-growing role of international courts, their place in a globalizing legal order, and their impact on politics and society at large. To understand these crucial and contemporary interplays of law, politics, and society, iCourts hosts a set of deeply integrated interdisciplinary research projects on the causes and consequences of the proliferation of international courts.

iCourts opened in March 2012. The centre is funded by a large grant from the Danish National Research Foundation (for the period 2012-18).

1.	INTRODUCTION.....	5
2.	READING TRANSFORMATION AS A CONSTITUTIONAL IMAGINARY	7
3.	THE ESSAY: INTERPRETING AND MAKING THE COMMUNITY CONSTITUTIONAL.....	10
(a)	Transformation’s brief genealogy.....	10
(b)	1958-1992: Changing equilibrium between Exit, Voice and Loyalty	13
(c)	Beyond 1992: The ideology, ethos and political culture of European integration.....	18
4.	COMMUNITARIAN UTOPIA WITH LIBERAL-LEGALIST IDEOLOGY	21
(a)	Transformation’s liberal legalism	22
(b)	Liberal legalism’s ideology: Creating the Community of Law.....	26
(c)	Communitarian utopia.....	30
5.	IDEOLOGY CRITIQUE: MAKING VISIBLE WHAT TRANSFORMATION CONCEALS.....	34
(a)	History as argument.....	35
(b)	The neglect of political economy.....	38
6.	CONCLUSION: SO, WHY READ IT TODAY?.....	40

1. Introduction

Almost everybody in the field of European studies would probably agree that Joseph Weiler's article, published first in 1991,¹ has been one of the most influential pieces written on European integration and its law.² But should we read the essay today? Is it a true classic, in the sense that despite its age it still speaks to us – *today*?

The answer to this question relates to what I will call here 'European constitutional imaginaries' – sets of ideas and beliefs that help to motivate and at the same time justify the European integration process and particularly its current form – the European Union as transformed by the series of crises that began in 2008. Reading *Transformation* today may help us understand the limits of liberal constitutional imaginary, on which *Transformation* builds and which it helped to establish in the 1990s. Now, when 'Western liberalism' is on retreat,³ such critical reading may be indispensable for those who look for alternatives.

Transformation is revealingly ambiguous about Europe. It partly builds on a constitutional imaginary that borrows from liberal, United-States-inspired constitutionalism which resonated globally at the time of its publication in 1991.⁴ It was a structure for a new world order at the 'end of history'⁵ that put emphasis on individual freedom, its juridical guarantees, and the free market. The unique context of that era made this imaginary particularly influential. There is a second part to the article, however, much more critical of the European Community's development after the adoption of the Single European Act in 1986. Here Joseph Weiler builds on a different imaginary, which seems to contradict *Transformation*'s first, analytical part. It calls for building a community, rather than a unity, where 'nationality and state affiliation of the individual, so divisive in the past' will be removed 'as the principal referent for transnational human intercourse'.⁶

¹ Joseph H.H. Weiler, 'The Transformation of Europe' (1991) 100 *Yale Law Journal* 2403-2483. Throughout this article I refer to it as *Transformation*.

² See particularly Miguel Poiaras Maduro and Marlene Wind (eds), *The Transformation of Europe: Twenty-Five Years On* (Cambridge: CUP 2017), 100.

³ Edward Luce, *The Retreat of Western Liberalism* (London: Little, Brown 2017).

⁴ For a triumphalist statement illustrating this thesis see Bruce Ackerman, 'The Rise of World Constitutionalism' (1997) 83 *Virginia Law Review* 771-797.

⁵ See Francis Fukuyama, *The end of history and the last man* (New York: Free Press 1992).

⁶ *Transformation*, 2481.

European constitutionalism – of all sorts - was in decline after the failure of the Constitutional Treaty.⁷ The need to adopt a new constitutional settlement has not been seen as a further step in European integration, but as an obstacle better to be avoided. Remarkably, the recently published *Franco-German non-paper on key questions and guidelines for the Conference on the Future of Europe* does not mention the word “constitution” at all.⁸ This is hardly surprising if it is true that even a Treaty change must not be mentioned in the debate on the future of Europe.⁹

The decline of European constitutionalism however does not mean that we cannot learn from reading *Transformation*. To the contrary, uncovering the article’s ‘deep structure’, and resurrecting its imaginary, can help us avoid falling into the same traps, such as celebrating the European Court of Justice’s bold judgments concerning the rule of law crisis¹⁰ or making legalistic attempts to tackle the growing disagreement about constitutional fundamentals in the EU.¹¹ This is the aim of this article, as part of a wider project that seeks to identify constitutional imaginaries of Europe. It also seeks to contribute to the debate on the crisis of liberal constitutionalism in the West.¹²

The article is structured as follows: Part 2 explains the central concept used here to shed new light on *Transformation*: constitutional imaginary. Part 3 provides a brief genealogy of *Transformation*, from a PhD thesis to an article published in a top US law review more than a decade later. This part also offers a critical reading of the whole essay, which prepares grounds for Part 4, where

⁷ The Treaty establishing a Constitution for Europe, concluded by the high contracting parties in 2004, was rejected in the French and Dutch referenda in the following year. After a ‘period of reflection’ the European Council officially abandoned the ‘constitutional concept’ – see Council of the European Union, Brussels, 20 July 2007, 11177/1/07, Brussels European Council of 21 and 22 June 2007, Presidency Conclusions, 15. On the whole process see e.g. Thomas Christiansen and Christine Reh, *Constitutionalizing the European Union* (London: Palgrave Macmillan 2009).

⁸ The link to the non-paper and related documents is available at <https://www.europeansources.info/record/conference-on-the-future-of-europe-2020-2022/> (22/06/2020).

⁹ See Maïa de la Baume, ‘Conference on the Future of Europe: Don’t mention the T word’, *Politico* 21 January 2020, available at <https://www.politico.eu/article/conference-on-the-future-of-europe-dont-mention-the-treaty-word-european-commission-parliament-ursula-von-der-leyen/> (22/06/2020).

¹⁰ See Armin von Bogdandy, ‘Principles of a systemic deficiencies doctrine: How to protect checks and balances in the Member States’ (2020) 57 *Common Market Law Review* 705-740, 712-713.

¹¹ See R. Daniel Kelemen, Piet Eeckhout, Federico Fabbrini, Laurent Pech, Renáta Uitz, ‘National Courts Cannot Override CJEU Judgments: A Joint Statement in Defense of the EU Legal Order’ *Verfassungsblog* 26 May 2020, <https://verfassungsblog.de/national-courts-cannot-override-cjeu-judgments/>.

¹² See Luce n 3.

Transformation's constitutional imaginary based on liberal-legalist ideology combined with a communitarian utopia is outlined. Part 5 addresses two additional components of *Transformation*'s imaginary: first, its rendering of European integration's history, reduced to the narrative of Europe's founding fathers' reflective choice for Europe and second, the ignorance of the questions of political economy. The conclusion finally connects these findings to the current issues facing the EU and liberal constitutionalism as such.

2. Reading Transformation as a constitutional imaginary

Before we turn to *Transformation* itself, we need to briefly define the key concept used here – constitutional imaginary.¹³ The term has been recently used by legal theorists,¹⁴ and sociologists,¹⁵ each tapping into various intellectual traditions and disciplines. It is used here in a rather idiosyncratic way, which is based on these works, but does not follow their definitions slavishly.¹⁶ I understand constitutional imaginaries as sets of *ideas and beliefs* that help to motivate and at the same time justify the practice of government and collective self-rule. They are as important as institutions and office-holders. They provide political action with an overarching *sense and purpose* recognized by those governed as legitimate. Constitutional imaginaries can be seen as 'necessary fictions' that make political rule possible,¹⁷ or as ideologies understood in (post-) Marxist terms as a 'means of domination'.¹⁸

¹³ A note on terminology: some authors make a distinction between imaginary and imagination, or use the term imagery. In this article I use the first, without however committing to any of possible distinctions.

¹⁴ See particularly Martin Loughlin, 'Constitutional Imagination' (2015) 78 *Modern Law Review* 1-25, who bases his account on Paul Ricoeur, *Lectures on ideology and utopia* (New York: Columbia University Press 1986). This has been the main inspiration for this article (and the whole project).

¹⁵ See Paul Blokker, 'The Imaginary Constitution of Constitutions' (2017) 3 *Social Imaginaries* 167-193

¹⁶ For a more detailed – yet preliminary – exploration of the concept see Jan Komárek, 'European Constitutional Imaginaries: Utopias, Ideologies and the *Other*' *IMAGINE Working Paper* No. 1 (*iCourts Working Paper Series*, No. 172), <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3477160>.

¹⁷ See Yaron Ezrahi, *Imagined Democracies: Necessary Political Fictions* (Cambridge: CUP 2012), 37.

¹⁸ See Susan Marks, *The riddle of all constitutions: International law, democracy, and the critique of ideology* (Cambridge: CUP 2000), 10.

Constitutional imaginaries may conceal from citizens some negative impacts of their central principles. Unconstrained commitment to international free trade agreements (as part of a neo-liberal imaginary)¹⁹ can make some people (feel) ‘left behind’ – and dominated by those who benefit from intensive international cooperation.²⁰ Beneficiaries of such an imaginary may not even realise their domination – until it is revealed by a radical result in a referendum or a presidential election as we saw after the Brexit vote or the election of Donald Trump to the presidency of the United States.²¹

Constitutional imaginary is therefore built on a tension, recently explored by Martin Loughlin in his Chorley lecture at the LSE.²² Imaginary – both at the level of an individual person who is co-producing it, and at the level of a society, where such imaginary forms part of its collective experience, is both ideological and utopian. It is ideological since in the interest of creating the society (or community), it suppresses the individual and her preferences, needs or experience. Any belonging to the collective is such; the alternative being the aggregate of individuals, each different in their own sphere, not shared with others except through contracting.²³ It is also utopian, since it gives the society a direction, or horizon – although it remains out of its reach.

A number of central concepts – ‘contested truths’ form part (not the whole) of a constitutional imaginary.²⁴ They are essential to the practice of government, and yet unsettled. It is around them

¹⁹ See Andrew Lang, *World Trade Law after Neoliberalism: Re-imagining the Global Economic Order* (Oxford: OUP 2011).

²⁰ See e.g. Dani Rodrik, *The Globalization Paradox: Why Global Markets, States, and Democracy Can't Coexist* (Oxford: OUP 2011).

²¹ For a revealing reflection of this by ‘a member of elite’ see – Robert Shrimmsley, ‘Brexit blues, or life as a victim of democracy’, *Financial Times* 4. 11. 2016, who notes: ‘For many, myself included, the referendum was the first real example of democracy being *something that is done to us*’ (emphasis added).

²² Loughlin, n 14. For a very useful account of the relationship between ideology and utopia in the work of various thinkers see Lyman Tower Sargent, ‘Ideology and Utopia’ in Michael Freeden, Lyman Tower Sargent and Mark Stears (eds), *The Oxford Handbook of Political Ideologies* (Oxford: OUP 2013), Chapter 24.

²³ This of course refers to the communitarian critique of liberalism, a debate that was ongoing in the United States at the end of 1980s and of which Weiler was clearly aware – see *Transformation*, 2480, fn 211.

²⁴ See particularly Daniel T. Rodgers, *Contested Truths. Keywords in American Politics since Independence* (Cambridge, Mass./London: HUP 1987) and Edward L. Rubin, *Beyond Camelot: Rethinking Politics and Law for the Modern State* (Princeton/Oxford: Princeton UP 2005). Constitutional imaginary is formed by words – since law (similarly to politics) is ‘a linguistically constituted activity’ (see Terence Ball, James Farr and Russel L. Hanson (eds),

that important political (and also legal-constitutional) arguments turn – be it the nature of statehood and sovereignty, the constitution and its identity, democracy, rights (human and/or fundamental), institutions that implement and protect them, etc. As Edward Rubin notes in his attempt to provide a new constitutional imaginary for the administrative state of the 20th century, ‘these words and concepts possess inherent ambiguities because they encompass our deepest value conflicts, and are sedimented with the multiple meanings that have been attached to them over many centuries of use’.²⁵ They are part of the conceptual vocabulary of modern public law and politics.²⁶

Lawyers, and especially more philosophically oriented lawyers with a foot in legal and political practice, are important co-producers of constitutional imaginaries.²⁷ Joseph Weiler represents one of them, arguably the most influential in the two decades between 1989 and the beginning of the Eurocrisis in 2010. His intellectual trajectory is therefore of interest not only for biographical reasons. The development from *Transformation* (as published in 1991) to Weiler’s late writings on Europe exemplifies Europe’s constitutional path, its *sonderweg*.²⁸ It is a path from Weiler’s hope (and belief) in supranational ‘integration through law’ of the 1980s to his critique of ‘integration through fear’²⁹ made in the aftermath of the Eurocrisis. It therefore provides an ideal starting point for a much wider inquiry into European constitutional imaginaries (in the plural) that have dominated the period from 1989 to 2008.

Political Innovation and Conceptual Change, Cambridge: CUP 1989). It however comprises images, architecture, visual arts and many other artefacts. See e.g. Kathleen R. McNamara, *The Politics of Everyday Europe: Constructing Authority in the European Union* (Oxford: OUP 2015).

²⁵ Rubin, n 24, 6.

²⁶ Explored e.g. by Martin Loughlin, *Foundations of Public Law* (Oxford: OUP 2010) or Ball et al., n 24. For an attempt in the context of European integration see András Jakab, *European Constitutional Language* (Cambridge: CUP 2016).

²⁷ As Rubin, n 24, notes at 11: ‘scholarship can be understood as an explicit expression of the conceptual process by which a modern society understands itself, and formulates its policies and plans’.

²⁸ Joseph Weiler, ‘In defence of the status quo: Europe’s constitutional *Sonderweg*’, in JHH Weiler and M Wind (eds), *European Constitutionalism Beyond the State* (Cambridge: CUP 2003), 7-23.

²⁹ Joseph Weiler, ‘Editorial: Integration through Fear’ (2012) 23 *European Journal of International Law* 1-5.

3. The essay: interpreting and making the Community constitutional

(a) Transformation's brief genealogy

The original essay appeared in 1991, but was in fact a culmination of Joseph Weiler's work on European integration that started in 1978. In that year, after graduating from the LL.M. programme of the Faculty of Law at the University of Cambridge, Weiler, as a research assistant, joined the project *Integration through law*, led by Mauro Cappelletti at the European University Institute in Florence.³⁰ As the early correspondence between Cappelletti and Weiler shows, the latter's interest in European integration was initially motivated by his concern with the Israel-Palestinian conflict.³¹ As he wrote some years later in an article that resulted from this original interest, '[p]articularly inspiring [was] the rehabilitation, of which the European Communities Common Market [was] a major facet, that brought former enemies together in a regional joint venture'.³² Through Weiler's involvement in *Integration through law* (and other policy-oriented projects conducted in Florence at that time),³³ however, his focus was shifting more and more towards

³⁰ On the history of this project and Joseph Weiler's role in it see Rebekka Byberg, 'The History of the Integration Through Law Project: Creating the Academic Expression of a Constitutional Legal Vision for Europe' (2017) 18 *German Law Journal* 1531-1556. I would like to express my deepest gratitude to Rebekka and her PhD thesis supervisor Morten Rasmussen for sharing with me the archive of Mauro Cappelletti, held by the *Historical Archives of the European Union*.

³¹ The original title of his dissertation was thus 'The Potential Application of Supranational Principles in the Middle East' and was co-supervised by two Israeli scholars, Nathan Feinberg, then Professor Emeritus at the Hebrew University, and Professor David Vital of the Tel-Aviv University. See letter from Nathan Feinberg to Terence Daintith, 16 May 1982 and letter from Joseph Weiler to Mauro Cappelletti, 27 October 1980, both on file with the *Historical Archives of the European Union*, Mauro Cappelletti).

³² See Joseph H. Weiler, 'Israel and the Creation of a Palestinian State: The Art of the Impossible and the Possible' (1982) 17 *Texas International Law Journal* 287-385, 330.

³³ Particularly *Control of Foreign Policy in Western Democracies: A Comparative Study of Parliamentary Foreign Affairs Committees*, research project directed by Antonio Cassese, University of Florence. See Joseph Weiler (with quantitative analysis by François Petry, *The European Parliament and Its Foreign Affairs Committees* (New York: Oceana Publications 1982). It is worth exploring the very history of the EU's Department of Law of that time, and the influence that Integration through Law had on its future identity as the central institution promoting constitutional imaginary set in motion by *Transformation*.

Europe, especially after having received very encouraging feedback from lawyers from within the field.³⁴ The first elaboration of some major themes that form the core of *Transformation* then appears as a working paper of the EUI Law Department in 1981³⁵ and as an article published in the very first volume of *Yearbook of European Law* in the same year.³⁶ The Middle-East never disappears from Joseph Weiler's academic agenda, but it becomes rather marginal.³⁷

Another important element in *Transformation*'s genealogy is a piece written as a reaction to political scientists' and international relations scholars' scepticism towards supranationalism and the prospects of European integration in general. Such scepticism was widespread at the time when Weiler worked on his doctoral dissertation.³⁸ The conference of "Europeanists" in Washington, DC in October 1980 was perhaps the moment when he realized the gap in the understanding of European integration between lawyers like him and the other two disciplines. He therefore started to "teach" the latter about the importance of law.³⁹ The piece and the whole encounter of Joseph Weiler with the other two disciplines was crucial for *Transformation*'s later scholarly influence. It is because what Weiler described as 'the "constitutionalisation" of the Community legal structure' was taken few years later (in the early 1990s) by a new generation of political science and

³⁴ See especially letter from Weiler to Cappelletti, 27 October 1980, where Weiler mentions expressly Neville Brown and Francis Jacobs.

³⁵ 'Supranationalism Revisited: Retrospective and Prospective. The European Communities After Thirty Years', *EUI Working Paper* No. 2, available at <http://hdl.handle.net/1814/23228>.

³⁶ Joseph Weiler, 'The Community System: the Dual Character of Supranationalism' (1984) 1 *Yearbook of European Law* 267-306. The PhD dissertation was defended only in June 1982 after these two pieces were published. It was entitled *Supranational law and the supranational system: Legal structure and political process in the European Community*. The thesis is available here: <http://hdl.handle.net/1814/4822>.

³⁷ The part of Weiler's original research devoted to the Middle East was first published as Weiler, n 32 and later as a book *Israel and the Creation of a Palestinian State: A European Perspective* (London: Croom Helm 1985). See also Ilan Greilsammer and Joseph Weiler (eds), *Europe and Israel: Troubled Neighbours* (Berlin/New York: W. de Gruyter 1988).

³⁸ Joseph Weiler, 'Community, Member States and European Integration: Is the Law Relevant?' (1982) 21 *Journal of Common Market Studies* 39-56. See also Weiler's observations in Weiler, n 32, 331-333.

³⁹ The piece referred to in n 38 begins (at 39), without reference, with a direct quotation from Stanley Hofmann, 'Reflections on the Nation-State in Western Europe Today' (1982) 21 *Journal of Common Market Studies* 21-37 – 'as Stanley Hofmann aptly suggest, "[t]oday's reality is complex and messy'. In one of the lectures in the Total Law course of 2006 Weiler referred to this conference as the moment when he realized the gap.

international relations scholars (Anne Marie Slaughter, Andrew Moravcsik, Karen Alter and others) as something that *correctly describes* the state of law (which they, as outsiders to the discipline, could not independently assess, only accept).⁴⁰ *Transformation* undoubtedly helped to put law and international cooperation/integration through law on the agenda of these disciplines.⁴¹

Eventually, *Transformation* was published as part of the *Yale Law Journal* international law symposium, which had been organised to commemorate the journal's centenary in 1991. Weiler was suggested to the student editors by Harold Koh, who then taught a course on international business transactions at Yale. As the student editor recently recalls the spirit of the time, "International law" in a US academic institution was very different then than it is today. It was considered a speciality that most lawyers wouldn't know much about or run into in their daily practice, but there was growing interest in the subject'.⁴² They did not expect that the essay would have that much impact outside the United States.

There is a clear break in the middle of the essay, separating what may be seen as a more analytical part, building on all these earlier works published in the 1980s, and the part entitled 'Beyond 1992: Two Visions of the Promised Land: The Ideology, Ethos and Political Culture of European integration', which has been added to this original analysis much later – probably when the essay was being drafted for the *Yale Law Journal*. If the nexus between law and politics of European integration was the primary focus of the first part, the second part deals with 'the modern contribution of Europe to the civilization of interstate and intrastate intercourse'.⁴³ The first part is very much about 'equilibrium theory' and European law's *authority*, whereas the second argues for the vision of integration as a community rather than unity and concerns European law's *legitimacy*.

⁴⁰ I owe this point to Karen Alter. See Morten Rasmussen and Dorte Sindbjerg Martinsen, 'EU constitutionalisation revisited: Redressing a central assumption in European studies' (2019) 25 *European Law Journal* 251-272 for a view that in the actual legal and political practice this was far from true.

⁴¹ See particularly Anne-Marie Slaughter, Andrew S. Tulumello and Stepan Wood, 'International Law and International Relations Theory: A New Generation of Interdisciplinary Scholarship' (1998) 92 *American Journal of International Law* 367-397, which reviews this development.

⁴² Email to the author from Nancy Dickinson, Yale Law School, Class of 1991 (J.D.), 11/06/2020. I am very grateful to her for sharing these memories with me.

⁴³ *Transformation*, 2483.

Both chiefly contributed to the vision of European Communities (and later the Union) as a *constitutional entity*, a view that became mainstream in the 1990s.

It is for this reason that the focus of this article remains the version as published in 1991. Two afterwards that were published in 1999 and 2017,⁴⁴ when *Transformation*'s imaginary was already firmly embedded in European studies (and also practical politics). Weiler's later works on European integration will occasionally be referred to; but the point of this article is to understand *Transformation*'s role in setting up a constitutional imaginary that was dominant – at least in EU academic circles – from the 1990s until the failure of the Constitutional Treaty in 2005 and, as will be discussed in the conclusion to this article, still informs the view of many in the discipline. After briefly revisiting the content of the original essay, its imaginary will be unfolded in the following part of this article.

(b) 1958-1992: Changing equilibrium between Exit, Voice and Loyalty

The analytical part of *Transformation* is organised in chronological order, distinguishing several periods in the EU's development between 1958 and 1992. It uses a specific methodological tool to demarcate the different periods: the interaction between law and politics, presented as a changing dynamics between selective Exit, that is the possibility of an individual member state to depart from the commonly agreed rules, and Voice, which stands for individual states' power to influence the content of such rules. The concepts of Exit and Voice are taken from Albert Hirschman's influential book *Exit, voice, and loyalty: responses to decline in firms, organizations, and states*.⁴⁵ Importantly, Weiler proposes 'first to discuss in *legal* categories the Exit option in the European Community [... and] then introduce Voice in *political* categories',⁴⁶ a disciplinary distinction that has a bearing on the overall analysis, as I explain below.

The 'Foundational Period' (1958 to mid-1970s)⁴⁷ is marked by the gradual closure of Selective Exit ('selective' as it refers to 'exiting' from *particular* obligations resulting from the Community

⁴⁴ The first was published in Weiler's collection of essays, Weiler (1999), 96-101, the other in Maduro/Wind, n 2, 333-351.

⁴⁵ HUP 1970.

⁴⁶ *Transformation*, 2412, emphasis edited.

⁴⁷ Note the year with which the analysis begins: 1958 – something I take issue with below in Part 5.

membership rather than leaving the Community altogether)⁴⁸ and the related pressure to get an enhanced Voice by national governments. Weiler calls this interaction between Exit and Voice the ‘equilibrium theory’, which in his view

*could even be part of a general theory of international law-making ... and posits a relationship between “hard law” and “hard law-making.” The “harder” the law in terms of its binding effect both on and within states, the less willing states are to give up their prerogative to control the emergence of such law or the law’s “opposability” to them. When the international law is “real”, when it is “hard” in the sense of being binding not only on but also in states, and when there are effective legal remedies to enforce it, decision- making suddenly becomes important, indeed crucial.*⁴⁹

‘Hard law’ established in the foundational period was formed by ‘four doctrines that fixed the relationship between Community law and Member State law’⁵⁰: direct effect, supremacy, implied powers and human rights. In Weiler’s view, these doctrines rendered the relationship between the Community and its Member States ‘*indistinguishable from analogous legal relationships in constitutional federal states*’.⁵¹ The ‘constitutional federal state’ Weiler had in mind was most likely

⁴⁸ In ‘Alternatives to Withdrawal from an International Organization: The Case of The European Economic Community’ (1985) 20 *Israel Law Review* 282-298 Weiler argues that unilateral withdrawal from the EEC is legally not permitted, although ‘it is unlikely that other Member States would use legal means to try and prevent such withdrawal’ (p. 288). Moreover, it is not likely that a withdrawing Member State would leave without protracted negotiations, given its embeddedness in the Community structures.

⁴⁹ *Transformation*, 2426, emphasis in the original. For the reception of this theory in IR see e.g. Anne-Marie Slaughter Burley, ‘International Law and International Relations Theory: A Dual Agenda’ (1993) 87 *American Journal of International Law* 205-239, 234-235.

⁵⁰ *Transformation*, 2413.

⁵¹ *Transformation*, 2413.

the United States, as some express references,⁵² but also less direct allusions dispersed throughout the text suggest.⁵³

The political side of the equilibrium gets comparatively less attention in the analysis of the foundational period. It focuses mostly on governments' pressure to enhance their control over Voice, which materialized through the Luxembourg compromise.⁵⁴ Already there, however, the essay raises some difficult questions about the legitimacy of the whole construct, especially the democratic deficit, consisting in the dominance of the executives over the decision-making process, and the lack of accountability of national governments. Weiler notes that 'it was not simply the Voice of the Member States that was enhanced, but the Voice of "governments"'⁵⁵ – at the expense of elected bodies.

The foundational period is followed by the 'Period of the Mutation' of the Community's jurisdiction, dated by Weiler from 1973 to mid 1980s. While this period was 'traditionally considered a stagnant epoch in European integration',⁵⁶ 'another large-scale mutation in the constitutional architecture of the Community took place',⁵⁷ according to Weiler. This was because the Community started to intervene in far more policy areas previously left (or reserved) to the Member States. This occurred through both *expansion* by legislation, principally through the

⁵² For example at 2403: 'In public discourse, "Europe" increasingly means the European Community in much the same way that "America" means the United States', at 2413: 'Effectively, individuals in real cases and controversies (usually against state public authorities) became the principal "guardians" of the legal integrity of Community law within Europe similar to the way that individuals in the United States have been the principal actors in ensuring the vindication of the Bill of Rights and other federal law', or at 2441, explaining the term 'incorporation' as 'borrowed from the constitutional history of the United States'.

⁵³ For example at 2443, where Weiler calls Article 235 TEEC the Community's 'necessary and proper provision' – whereas the US Constitution has its 'necessary and proper clause' in Article I, Section 8 or at 2481: 'the life of the Community ... is not logic, but experience' – alluding to the famous quote from the U.S. Supreme Court's justice O.W. Holmes book, *The Common Law* (first published in 1881), which read: 'The life of the law has not been logic: it has been experience'. It is true that such allusions and invocations were most likely due to the place where *Transformation* was published – an American law review.

⁵⁴ *Transformation*, 2423. The Luxembourg compromise gave every Member State an effective veto over the decisions to be adopted by the Council, if they run counter its 'very important interests'.

⁵⁵ *Transformation*, 2403.

⁵⁶ *Transformation*, 2431.

⁵⁷ *Transformation*, 2431.

generous use of the ‘implied powers clause’ (then Article 235 TEEC), and through the decisions of the European Court of Justice, which interpreted the scope of Community’s competences rather generously.

These ‘mutations’ led Weiler to engage in a number of normative reflections. First, he raised ‘the question of constitutionality’, which essentially amounted to questioning the collapse of the division of competences between the Member States and the Community. The concern here seems to be the acceptance by ‘a new community of interpretation, in which the European Court and Member State courts play complementary roles’⁵⁸ and again, accountability. The second question was much deeper and had to do with the distortion of ‘the balance of social and political forces in the decisional game at both the Member State and Community level’.⁵⁹ As we shall see, however, *Transformation* refrains from analysing these various forces – a feature of the essay (and I would argue of most of the scholarship which builds on *Transformation*’s constitutional imaginary), to which I will return.⁶⁰

The final period examined by *Transformation* begins with the adoption of the Single European Act and the launch of the 1992 internal market programme in 1986. The key change was the turn from unanimity to qualified majority voting introduced by Article 100a TEEC – a provision that was intended to have (and then actually had) a large impact on the overall decision-making structure of the Community.⁶¹ For Weiler this meant that ‘the foundational equilibrium, despite attempts to rescue it in the actual drafting of the SEA, seem[ed] to be shattered’.⁶² Combination of effects brought about by the two previous periods (hardening of their obligations and the loss of control over the Community’s jurisdictional limits) means that ‘Member States thus face not only the constitutional normativity of measures adopted often wholly or partially against their will, but also the operation of this normativity in a vast area of public policy’.⁶³

⁵⁸ *Transformation*, 2451.

⁵⁹ *Transformation*, 2453.

⁶⁰ See Part 5.

⁶¹ *Transformation*, 2459.

⁶² *Transformation*, 2462 – the attempts mentioned by Weiler refer mainly to Article 100a (4), which provided for an exception from the general harmonizing measure. Weiler explains the limited use of it in the light of the overall decision-making structure in the Community.

⁶³ *Transformation*, 2463.

This change brought about two challenges, one of compliance and the other consisting of the double challenge of “democracy” and “legitimacy”.⁶⁴ Regarding compliance, Weiler raises another concept inspired by Hirschmann’s book: *Loyalty*.⁶⁵ In Weiler’s view loyalty can *replace* the foundational equilibrium and ‘become the constitutional reflex of the Member States and their organs’.⁶⁶ Importantly, ‘A Loyalty to the institution may have developed that breaks out of the need for constant equilibrium’,⁶⁷ resulting in a lower pressure to enhance Voice in response to the further reduction of (selective) Exit.

Regarding the challenge of democracy and legitimacy, Weiler argues that ‘[v]ery frequently in discourse about the Parliament and the Community the concepts of democracy and legitimacy have been presented interchangeably although in fact they do not necessarily coincide’.⁶⁸ Here we get to one of the questions that Joseph Weiler has never ceased to ask with regard European integration. Although at times Weiler is rather sceptical as regards the usefulness of the concept of legitimacy,⁶⁹ here he uses it to explain why the increase of powers of institutions that *formally* provide the Community with democratic legitimacy⁷⁰ may in fact make the matters worse when it comes to the Community’s *social* legitimacy – ‘a broad, empirically determined, societal acceptance of the system’.⁷¹ Such legitimacy ‘occurs when the government process displays a commitment to, and actively guarantees values that are part of the general political culture, such as justice, freedom, and general welfare’.⁷²

Drawing on the literature on political legitimacy in federal polities and international law,⁷³ Weiler identifies the key problem of the increasingly powerful integrated Community in the ‘loss of democracy’ *as perceived* by citizens of *individual* Member States, which lost control over certain

⁶⁴ Weiler puts these two concepts into quotation marks himself.

⁶⁵ Hirschman, n 45.

⁶⁶ *Transformation*, 2465.

⁶⁷ *Ibid.*

⁶⁸ *Transformation*, 2468.

⁶⁹ Joseph Weiler, ‘Epilogue: Judging the Judges – Apology and Critique’ in Maurice Adams et al (eds), *Judging Europe’s Judges. The Legitimacy of the Case Law of the European Court of Justice* (Oxford: Hart 2013), 235.

⁷⁰ In the 1980s’s discourse of ‘democratic deficit’ the European Parliament was believed to be such an institution.

⁷¹ *Transformation*, 2468.

⁷² *Transformation*, 2469.

⁷³ See *Transformation*, 2466, fn 181 for the works cited by Weiler.

kinds of policies and see the Community as less responsive to their demands than their own governments. Such citizens do not accept the Community as their relevant polity, in which they would accept decisions of a majority (contrary to what they habitually do in the context of their own national polities). In Weiler's view, there are two ways to address this kind of legitimacy problem: *The first is a visible and tangible demonstration that the total welfare of the citizenry is enhanced as a result of integration. The second answer is ensuring that the new integrated polity itself, within its new boundaries, has democratic structures. But more important still is giving a temporarily enhanced Voice to the separate polities.*⁷⁴

The two answers would today be probably presented as the need to provide for input and output legitimacy.⁷⁵ The last sentence in the paragraph quoted above adds a particular twist, however: it suggests that generating social legitimacy is a *process*. To determine whether the enhanced Voice (which amounts to a veto by individual Member State) is *still* necessary is a matter not of theoretical, but of practical judgment.⁷⁶ Weiler thus asks 'whether the time is ripe for a radical change toward a more federal structure, or whether the process should continue in a more evolutionary fashion'.⁷⁷ The question is left unanswered, but Weiler's later opposition to the adoption of the "Constitutional Treaty"⁷⁸ indicates what Weiler thought already in 1991: he rejected the radical change.

(c) Beyond 1992: The ideology, ethos and political culture of European integration

The final part of the original essay, entitled 'Beyond 1992: Two Visions of the Promised Land: the Ideology, Ethos, and Political Culture of European Integration', is devoted to the kind of reflection that the readers of Weiler's work got used to in the 1990s.⁷⁹ Weiler acts as a 'living conscience' of

⁷⁴ *Transformation*, 2471, emphasis added.

⁷⁵ On these notions see Fritz Scharpf, *Governing in Europe: Effective and Democratic?* (Oxford: OUP 1999).

⁷⁶ Cf. *Transformation*, 2471, fn. 192 - Weiler's approvingly quoting Robert A. Dahl, 'Federalism and the Democratic Process' in JR Pennock and JW Chapman (eds), *Liberal Democracy XXV Nomos* (NYU Press 1983), 95-108 at 106

⁷⁷ *Transformation*, 2472.

⁷⁸ See 'On the power of the Word: Europe's constitutional iconography' (2005) 3 *International Journal of Constitutional Law* 173-190.

⁷⁹ Collected in Weiler (1999), n 2.

the integration process providing it with a very strong (and critical) moral (or moralizing) compass. Weiler reflects on the change quite openly:

In the earlier parts of this chapter I rested my interpretation, as much as possible and at least in its factual matrix, on an “objective” reality rooted in “empirical” and consequently “refutable” data. Likewise, my analytical moves were transparent enough to open them to rational critique. Obvious and inevitable limitations on the resulting “scientific objectivity” of the chapter exist. Clearly, to give the most banal example, my own prejudices, overt and less overt, shaped the selection of factual data, and, of course, their perception and analysis. Readers are always better placed than the writer to expose those prejudices and discount them in assessing the overall picture.

In turning to ethos, ideology, and political culture, the screening process of the “self” (my “self”) plays an even bigger role in the narrative. To try to “document” my assertions and conclusions here would be to employ the semblance of a scholarly apparatus where it is patently not merited. I do not, and cannot, claim to root this part of the chapter on the kind of painstaking research and complex tools that characterize the work of the social historian or the historical sociologist. Caveat lector!⁸⁰

It is telling that Weiler does not want to pretend that even the analytical part is completely free of bias. It reflects the crisis in social sciences that resonated throughout American law schools in the 1980s⁸¹ – precisely at the time when Weiler left Europe and started his career there as a professor at the University of Michigan Law School where he served as a successor to Eric Stein.⁸² A sort of ‘hermeneutic of suspicion’⁸³ pervades the essay – and yet there are ideological elements that need to be highlighted in order to understand the effect of *Transformation* in terms of the particular constitutional imaginary it established.

Weiler observes the absence of the right-left ideological debate in the Community (especially in the pre-1992 Community), while at the same time there is an ‘abundant discourse on the politics and

⁸⁰ *Transformation*, 2474, n 195.

⁸¹ See Laura Kalman, *The Strange Career of Legal Liberalism* (New Haven and London: Yale UP 1996), Chapter 4 or Arthur Austin, ‘The Postmodern Infiltration of Legal Scholarship’ (2000) 98 *Michigan Law Review* 1504-1528.

⁸² See Anne Boerger and Morten Rasmussen, ‘Transforming European Law: The Establishment of the Constitutional Discourse from 1950 to 1993’ (2014) 10 *European Constitutional Law Review* 199-225.

⁸³ Duncan Kennedy, ‘The Hermeneutic of Suspicion in Contemporary American Legal Thought’ (2014) 25 *Law Critique* 91-139.

choices of the integration model itself⁸⁴ (translated into much more practical and salient questions, such as how much power to leave for the Member States, or to particular institutions of the Community). Weiler predicted this state of things to change, since

*A 'single European market' is a concept which still has the power to stir. But it is also a 'single European market'. It is not simply a technocratic program to remove the remaining obstacles to the free movement of all factors of production. It is at the same time a highly politicized choice of ethos, ideology, and political culture: the culture of 'the market'.*⁸⁵

It is remarkable both how prescient – and at the same time how wrong - Weiler's prediction was about the change in the terms of the debate. Europe was turning into a market society, a process few people reflected on in the period of the uncontested reign of neoliberalism (early 1980s until 2008).⁸⁶ But even after the Euro-crisis many Europeans contest “Brussels” rather than international financial capitalism and the all-pervading market culture, which the EU represents, but certainly does not cause (alone).⁸⁷

Turning from the analytical mode of the preceding parts of his essay, Weiler presents the utopian side of his constitutional imaginary, ‘the two competing visions of the promised land’ – ‘Europe as unity and Europe as Community’.⁸⁸ The first shall result, ‘finally, in full political union, in some version of a federal United States of Europe’.⁸⁹ But that is not the preferred option, and Weiler continues:

The alternative vision, community, also rejects the classical model of international law which celebrates statal sovereignty, independence, and autonomy and sees international legal regulation providing a “neutral” arena for states to prosecute their own (“national”) goals premised on power and self-interest. The community vision is, instead, premised on limiting, or sharing, sovereignty in a select albeit growing number of fields, on recognizing, and even celebrating, the

⁸⁴ *Transformation*, 2474.

⁸⁵ *Transformation*, 2477

⁸⁶ See Vivien A. Schmidt and Mark Thatcher (eds), *Resilient Liberalism: European Political Economy through Boom and Bust* (Cambridge: CUP 2013).

⁸⁷ See Jan Komárek, ‘Waiting for the Existential Revolution in Europe’ (2014) 12 *International Journal of Constitutional Law* 190-212, 205-206.

⁸⁸ *Transformation*, 2478.

⁸⁹ *Transformation*, 2479.

*reality of interdependence, and on counterpoising to the exclusivist ethos of statal autonomy a notion of a community of states and peoples sharing values and aspirations.*⁹⁰

The key question, which is still relevant, almost thirty years since *Transformation* was published, is whether we can achieve such community with the kind of law analysed – and as I will show, also *created* - in the first part of Weiler's essay. Put into the key in which this article is written: can we build a community of states and peoples with a liberal-legalist constitutional imaginary? The following part of this article seeks to answer this question, which goes to the very heart of not only Joseph Weiler's work on European integration, but also much of the scholarship that builds on it.

4. Communitarian utopia with liberal-legalist ideology

Transformation seems to be embedded in two different – and as will be shown, two conflicting imaginaries. It appears as if the first, analytical, part of *Transformation* fought against the second, prescriptive (which had been written, and more importantly, thought through, at a later date). This may be a trite finding – why read it today, then (other than learning that even great scholars may not be fully consistent in their thinking)?

However, there is more at stake here. The tensions between the two parts of *Transformation* reveal something much more important: how the desire to build a *community* can be hampered by a *liberal-legalist* imaginary, which *at first had made it possible*. The question for today therefore is whether the realisation of the Community of Law (Walter Hallstein's *Rechtsgemeinschaft*)⁹¹ can be prevented by the very law which at first had set the whole process in motion (and even made it possible to imagine). That is of course something far more important, and it should concern anybody who still invokes a liberal-legalist imaginary today – in Europe or even globally. It may suggest that the time has come to move away from this imaginary and search for something different.

This part begins that task by first shedding more light on the notion of liberal legalism and its roots in the particular period of American law that Weiler entered when he moved from Florence to Michigan. Second, we will explore in more detail what makes (or has made) liberal legalism so attractive. In the third step, we move towards the communitarian utopia outlined by

⁹⁰ *Transformation*, 2479.

⁹¹ See Kaarlo Tuori, *European Constitutionalism* (Cambridge: CUP 2015), 212-214.

Transformation, and discuss how liberal legalism stands as an obstacle to it becoming a new constitutional imaginary.

(a) Transformation's liberal legalism

Overall, despite being written about Europe, *Transformation* is embedded in the American culture of liberal legalism that had been dominant at law schools in the United States until the mid-1980s.⁹² As the legal historian Laura Kalman describes it, 'legal liberalism' refers to 'trust in the potential of courts, particularly the Supreme Court, to bring about "those specific social reforms that affect large groups of people, [...]"; in other words, *policy change with nationwide impact*'.⁹³ It reflected the apparent success of the Warren Court in the Civil Rights Revolution of the 1960s,⁹⁴ the third 'constitutional moment' in the constitutional history of the United States.⁹⁵

Kalman uses the term legal *liberalism* rather than liberal *legalism*, since she finds the latter, 'as a political and legal liberal... unduly pejorative'.⁹⁶ There is however a deeper distinction between the two. Kalman's politics is liberal, in the sense that would be probably identified with the politics of

⁹² See Nomi Maya Stolzenberg, 'Book Review: A Book of Laughter and Forgetting: Kalman's "Strange Career" and the Marketing of Civic Republicanism' (1998) 111 *Harvard Law Review* 1025-1084, 1025, extensive review of Kalman, n 81. "Dominance" does not mean that it was the only approach to law during that time. Another review of Kalman's book is titled, tellingly, 'Legal liberalism at Yale' (Stephen M. Griffin, (1997) *Constitutional Commentary* 535-555) and characterizes (at 535) the book as 'an account of the reaction of ten legal scholars to the Supreme Court's conservative turn in the 1970s and 1980s'. For several decades liberal legalism however framed the terms of the debate over the Constitution – even if its conclusions (and prescriptions) were hotly contested by its opponents. See also Steven M. Teles, *The rise of the conservative legal movement: The battle for control of the law* (Princeton: PUP 2008) for an account of how the liberal dominance provoked a counter-movement.

⁹³ Kalman, n 81, 2, emphasis in the original, quoting from Gerald Rosenberg, *The Hollow Hope: Can Courts Bring about Social Change?* (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press 1996), 4. This latter book was one that helped to shatter that trust with a rigorous empirical analysis of the impact on the American society of some key Supreme Court's decisions.

⁹⁴ See Kalman, n 81, Chapter 1.

⁹⁵ 'Constitutional moment' was the term coined by one of the prominent legal liberals: Bruce Ackerman in his influential trilogy *We the People*. For a critical review see Michael J. Klarman, 'Constitutional Fact/Constitutional Fiction: A Critique of Bruce Ackerman's Theory of Constitutional Moments' (1992) 44 *Stanford Law Review* 759-797.

⁹⁶ Kalman, n 81, 265, n 52.

the Democratic Party today.⁹⁷ Legalism, and liberal legalism in particular, has been the term used by critics who may have had all sorts of politics in mind, however, some of them rejecting the constitutional system of the United States and the kind of politics (and political economy) it has helped to sustain completely.⁹⁸ Related to the exalted role for the Supreme Court, there are a number of other assumptions that liberal legalism makes:

*that law and politics are and should be separate, that legal judgments should be made impartially and should adhere to rules articulated and known in advance, that power should be exercised in accordance with the rule of law, that governments should recognise and respect rights, and that freedom rather than equality should be the highest political value.*⁹⁹

At first, it seems that *Transformation* aims at going beyond the legalist ideology exposed by its critics. Weiler seems to have taken a proper lesson from the (now rather over-quoted) observation by the U.S. political scientist Martin Shapiro, for whom most writing on Community law represent[ed] ‘constitutional law without politics’, ‘a stage of constitutional scholarship out of which American constitutional law must have passed about seventy years ago’.¹⁰⁰ However, ‘constitutional law without politics’ is only replaced by liberal legalism,¹⁰¹ which makes much of its politics invisible and closes it to contestation.

⁹⁷ Kalman, n 81, 247, n 1, refers to William A Galston, *Liberal Purposes: Goods, Virtues, and Diversity in the Liberal State* (Cambridge: CUP 1991).

⁹⁸ See Kalman, n 81, 85-86. For a representative collection of essays dealing critically with liberal legalism, as represented by Ronald Dworkin’s *Law’s Empire* (Cambridge, Mass.: Belknap Press 1986), see Alan Hunt (ed), *Reading Dworkin Critically* (Oxford: Berg 1992).

⁹⁹ Austin Sarat, ‘Going to Court: Access, Autonomy, and the Contradictions of Liberal Legality’ in David Kairys (ed), *The Politics of Law: A Progressive Critique*, 3rd Ed (New York: Basic Books 1998), 97-114, 97.

¹⁰⁰ Martin Shapiro, ‘Comparative Law and Politics’ (1980) 53 *Southern California Law Review* 537-542, 538. Weiler quotes this passage already in the opening pages to his PhD thesis (n 36, 1-2), where he states: ‘The primary goal of my own study will be precisely to meet this critique of, and challenge to, European legal literature’. For a spirited reaction, which may be read as a response to Weiler too, see , Anthony Arnull, ‘The Americanization of EU law Scholarship’ in Anthony Arnull, Piet Eeckhout, and Takis Tridimas (eds), *Continuity and Change in EU Law: Essays in Honour of Sir Francis Jacobs* (OUP 2008), 415-431.

¹⁰¹ It goes beyond the scope of this essay to examine the influence of Joseph Weiler’s move to the United States; another indication of that influence, however, may be the title of an article that dealt with the legitimacy of the ECJ: ‘Eurocracy and Distrust: Some Questions Concerning the Role of the European Court of Justice in the Protection of Fundamental Human Rights within the Legal Order of the European Communities, (1986) 61 *Washington Law Review*

First, the analytical part of *Transformation* exhibits the trust in courts (especially the ECJ) similar to that of legal liberals discussed by Kalman. Consider e.g. the following observation, concerning the role of courts in the ‘Foundational Period’ and the question of how the profound changes of that period could ‘occur with a minimal measure of political (i.e., Member State) opposition’:

[p]art of the answer rests, of course, in the fact that constitutionalization during the foundational period was judicially driven, thus attaching to itself that deep-seated legitimacy that derives from the mythical neutrality and religious-like authority with which we invest our supreme courts.¹⁰²

Second, *Transformation* significantly overestimates the force of law (and legal institutions), when it assesses the impact of the ECJ’s rulings on the behaviour of other actors:

A national court opinion takes care of the most dramatic weakness of the Article 169 procedure: the ability of a Member State, in extremis, to disregard the strictures of the European Court. Under the Article 177 procedure this disregard is impossible. A state, in our Western democracies, cannot disobey its own courts.¹⁰³

1103-1142, whose title is clearly inspired by John Hart Ely, *Democracy and Distrust: A Theory of Judicial Review* (Cambridge, Mass.: HUP 1980), one of the most influential defenses of the Warren Court and its liberal legalism.

¹⁰² *Transformation*, 2428. One may question to what extent this exalted role given to courts could fit Europe of 1960s or 1970s. With a possible exception of the German Federal Constitutional Court, which had been only slowly building its authority at that time (see Justin Collings, *Democracy’s Guardians: A History of the German Federal Constitutional Court, 1951–2001*, Oxford: OUP 2015, Chapter 2), courts had been seen in Europe as bodies possessing the kind of formal-legal rationality that made them almost part of state bureaucracies. There was nothing mystical or religious about them. For an extremely pertinent legal-cultural observations concerning the US and France, see Antoine Garapon and Ioannis Papadopoulos, *Juger en Amérique et en France: Culture juridique française et common law* (Paris: Odile Jacob 2003).

¹⁰³ *Transformation*, 2421, emphasis in the last sentence added. Article 169 refers to what is now Article 258 TFEU setting out infringement procedure, whereby the Commission can take a Member State, failing in its obligations under EU law, to the ECJ. Article 177 is now Article 267 TFEU, concerning the preliminary ruling procedure, whereby a national court may (and sometimes must) refer questions concerning EU law to the ECJ. *Transformation* adds that ‘the attempts of Member States to practice selective Community membership by disregarding their obligations have become regularly adjudicated before their own national courts’ (p. 20) and ‘The combination of the “constitutionalization” and the system of judicial remedies to a large extent nationalized Community obligations and introduced on the Community level the *habit of obedience* and the respect for the rule of law which traditionally is less associated with international obligations than national ones’ (p. 21, emphasis in the original) – these were unproven propositions in 1991 and they remain so today.

Third, law is portrayed throughout *Transformation* as a means to close the ‘Selective Exit’- in other words, to constrain Member States’ freedom of action. However, law does the opposite too – it makes politics possible by structuring its processes and creating institutions where politics can be conducted.¹⁰⁴ It is misleading to portray the law as something that only limits the ‘Voice’ of (international) politics. Law is one of the languages that the Voice speaks – and has impact on what is going to be prescribed. The kind of law used to express politics then influences policy outcomes, and more widely, the whole culture in which law is embedded. In case of the EU, it is sometimes compared to the American culture of ‘adversarial legalism’: regulatory style that relies on litigation as the key mode of governance.¹⁰⁵ It puts emphasis on individual rights and lawyers who defend those rights in front of courts. It fits the kind of politics that is possible in the EU – but also constrains it in ways that *Transformation* probably did not see.¹⁰⁶

There are other markers of liberal legalism in the essay: the emphasis on judicial remedies as a measure of constitutionalisation,¹⁰⁷ the reference to the human rights scrutiny as a ‘surrogate’ for democracy,¹⁰⁸ or the praise for the Court for its ‘stepp[ing] in to hold the construct together’ when the ‘political will among the Member States to follow the decision- making processes of the Treaty and to develop a loyalty to the European venture’ was declining.¹⁰⁹

One may even argue that the key methodological premise of the analytical part (Weiler proposes ‘first to discuss in *legal* categories the Exit option in the European Community [... and] then introduce Voice in *political* categories’),¹¹⁰ is based on an idea of the autonomy of law from

¹⁰⁴ See especially Martin Loughlin, *Political Jurisprudence* (Oxford: OUP 2017), 20. For this point made in the context of EU law see Gráinne de Búrca, ‘Rethinking law in neofunctionalist theory’ (2005) 12 *Journal of European Public Policy* 310–326, 319.

¹⁰⁵ On the notion see Robert A. Kagan, *Adversarial legalism: The American way of law* (Cambridge/London: HUP 2001). R. Daniel Kelemen, *Eurolegalism: The transformation of law and regulation in the European Union* (Cambridge/London: HUP 2011) makes this analysis in the context of EU law.

¹⁰⁶ See Scharpf, n 75.

¹⁰⁷ *Transformation*, 2419: ‘The constitutionalization claim regarding the Treaties establishing the European Community *can only be sustained* by adding one more layer of analysis: the system of judicial remedies and enforcement’ (emphasis added).

¹⁰⁸ *Transformation*, 2417: ‘This scrutiny is important given the “democracy deficit” in Community decision- making’.

¹⁰⁹ *Transformation*, 2425.

¹¹⁰ *Transformation*, 2411-12, emphasis added.

politics, which came under attack from many sides. Legal liberalism had been in deep crisis precisely in the period when *Transformation* was being turned from a PhD thesis into one of the most influential pieces on European integration. Laura Kalman, mentioned above, describes the crisis as coming mainly from within: from the continuous failure to find some “objective” grounds for interpretation of the Constitution; the realization, prompted by hermeneutics and the linguistic turn in philosophy that legal scholars are inevitably part of the game of the creation of the law’s meaning, no matter how “scientifically” they want to work and how detached from the object of their analysis they want to appear; and finally, from the kind of politics promoted by the successors to the Warren Court, which ceased to be “liberal” in the sense preferred by Kalman and the legal liberals discussed by her.¹¹¹

Weiler seems to be acutely aware of all these problems with legal liberalism and yet does not want to give up its goods, especially the establishment of the formal rule of law into the relationships among the member states and their citizens – no small achievement in post-war Europe. But there is more to liberal legalism than this, which makes it so hard to abandon it, as the following section shows.

(b) Liberal legalism’s ideology: Creating the Community of Law

Weiler himself characterizes the ‘concept of law’ employed in *Transformation* in the following way: ‘my synthesis and analysis are truly in the tradition of the “pure theory of law” with the riders that “law” encompasses a discourse that is much wider than doctrine and norms and that the very dichotomy of law and politics is questionable’.¹¹² The rejection of the dichotomy between law and politics does not imply the CLS credo “all law is politics” – and therefore illegitimate. Rather, it maintains the legitimacy of law by embracing – and internalizing - its political element. At the same time, it insists that law has its own rationality and that it is able to shape action and exercise agency autonomously from politics conducted outside the legal system. This idea is expressed by Weiler’s reference to the autopoietic theory of law, which to him ‘acknowledges a much greater role to

¹¹¹ See Kalman, n 81, Chapter 4.

¹¹² *Transformation*, 2409.

internal discourse of law in explaining its evolutionary dynamics'.¹¹³ External events are said to be 'mediated through the prism of the system and do not have a reality of their own'.¹¹⁴

In my view, however, Weiler does not subscribe to systems theory any more than he does to the pure theory of law.¹¹⁵ The important point he wants to make is one about the power of legal discourse – *even on those, who are its subjects and seasoned practitioners*. Law is something that transcends them – and has effects on them. In short, law (and legal doctrine) is ideological. As noted in Part 2 above, 'ideology' is not taken in a pejorative sense as a 'false consciousness', which needs to be displaced by some enlightened reason. Ideology, as part of constitutional imaginary, is inevitable, as it makes collective rule possible. It forms part (together with culture, language and social institutions), of what Jack Balkin calls the 'objective aspect of social life', which constrains social actors, including lawyers (in practice and academia alike).¹¹⁶ Ideology makes law intelligible (as it hides the contradictions on which law is built and turns law into a coherent system) and provides legal actors with a sense of constraint.¹¹⁷

The problem with ideology, however, is that very often its partisan (and partial) character is not realised and reflected upon. The prevailing view in the 'community of interpreters' (a term also employed by *Transformation*) will be considered as 'moderate' or 'balanced', whereas 'persons who deviate too much from the political norm are seen as ideologically driven or "radical", or even "unreasonable"'.¹¹⁸

Transformation oscillates between the liberal trust in courts (and law and legal rationality) and its critique. This reminds one of what Duncan Kennedy termed 'The Paradox of American Critical

¹¹³ *Transformation*, 2410, fn. 15. Weiler was probably influenced by a colleague at the EU, Günther Teubner. See Günther Teubner (ed), *Autopoietic law: A New Approach to Law and Society* (Berlin/New York: Walter de Gruyter 1988), collection of essays produced at the EUI.

¹¹⁴ *Transformation*, 2410, fn 15.

¹¹⁵ On this point see also Jakob V.H. Holtermann and Mikael Rask Madsen, 'Toleration, Synthesis or Replacement? The "Empirical Turn" and its Consequences for the Science of International Law' (2016) *19 Leiden Journal of International Law* 1001-1019, 1008-1009.

¹¹⁶ Jack M. Balkin, 'Ideology as Constraint' (1991) 43 *Stanford Law Review* 1133-1169, 1143 (a review essay on Andrew Altman, *Critical Legal Studies: A Liberal Critique* (Princeton: Princeton UP 1999)).

¹¹⁷ See Balkin, n 116 and also Jack M. Balkin, 'Taking Ideology Seriously: Ronald Dworkin and the CLS Critique' (1987) 55 *UMKC Law Review* 392-433, especially at 423-426.

¹¹⁸ Balkin, n 116, 1152.

Legalism’: ‘an odd combination of utter faith and utter distrust in law’.¹¹⁹ One of the central preoccupations of this kind of legalism was to maintain the distinction between law and politics (and courts and legislators), even in the context of ‘high stakes’, since too much – for both sides of conflict (described by Kennedy as liberals and conservatives) – have stood on maintaining such distinctions. Put succinctly, ‘if [Americans] did not have a common civic religion of law their heterogeneous society might fly to pieces’.¹²⁰ Belief in law holds America together.

Transformation exhibits this paradox too. Although it puts the law and politics nexus (and the relationship between the ECJ and national governments) at the heart of its analysis,¹²¹ it does so in a way that in fact makes the understanding of this relationship dependent on normative assumptions about law and politics that are never fully revealed. The reason for this may consist in Joseph Weiler’s faith in the integration project as a new way to organize inter-state and inter-human relationships, the hope with which he came to study Europe.¹²²

This, however, is not only due to such faith. As I will argue, it is inevitable, if we understand *Transformation* as a “law piece”, rather than one *about* law.¹²³ In other words, we must understand it as primarily a legal argument written for lawyers, not an “external analysis” intended solely for the scholarly discourse.¹²⁴

When *Transformation* says that *constitutional discipline* was introduced to the relationship between the Community and its Member States or that ‘[o]ne by one, the highest jurisdictions in the Member States accepted the new judicial architecture of Europe’,¹²⁵ it does not provide a mere analysis. It contributes to the discipline’s actual working, together with its acceptance by Member State courts and their institutions. This is further exemplified by several argumentative moves, such as the one about the almost logical inevitability of direct effect and supremacy in the construction of the

¹¹⁹ (1997) 3 *European Law Journal* 359-377, 359, reprinted from Chapter 4 of Duncan Kennedy, *A Critique of Adjudication [fin de siècle]* (Cambridge and London: HUP 1997).

¹²⁰ Kennedy (1997), n 119, 361.

¹²¹ The whole ‘equilibrium theory’ and the periodization of European integration stands on it. See n 49.

¹²² See the text at n 32.

¹²³ This refers to the distinction between “law books” and “books about law” – see Richard A. Abel, ‘Law Books and Books about Law’ (1973) 26 *Stanford Law Review* 175-228.

¹²⁴ For how problematic this distinction can be, see Charles L. Barzun, ‘Inside-Out: Beyond the Internal/External Distinction in Legal Scholarship’ (2015) 101 *Virginia Law Review* 1203-1288.

¹²⁵ *Transformation*, 2418.

Community's legal order. Consider this note, made by Weiler on this account: 'If one accepts, *as one must*, the principle of the uniform application of Community law throughout the Community, a clear link exists whereby a holding of direct effect compels a holding of supremacy'.¹²⁶ Uniformity in application of Community law is used as an axiom, on which everything else stands – regardless of its dubious implementation in most legal orders.¹²⁷

Such 'internal' analysis is insufficient, however. *Transformation* builds on constitutionalism's appeal as a 'higher law', not in terms of hierarchy, but as a civilizational achievement which stands on deep ideas and not 'mere' legal technicalities and bureaucratic rationality. Alexander Somek's recollection of his first reading of *Transformation* speaks a great deal about the understanding of Community law among those yet-uninitiated (that is, those who have not read *Transformation*): *From the pillar structure all the way down to the exposition of the co-decision procedure, I felt reminded of the most insufferable quarters of administrative law or commercial law. Not a trace of constitutional ideals, not even the cosmopolitan spirit of public international law. All that I encountered was the grey in grey of bureaucracy.*¹²⁸

Then, Somek adds, a colleague suggested to read *Transformation* and Somek 'began viewing the Union from the perspective of political philosophy'.¹²⁹ The Union and its law suddenly appeared colourful and worth attention.¹³⁰ It thus may be paradoxical to understand the enduring influence of *Transformation* only in terms of its analysis. Its aesthetics and one may say phenomenology – both in terms of the picture of European integration it offered and also as regards the style in which the essay is written were equally important.¹³¹

¹²⁶ *Transformation*, 2424, fn. 49, emphasis added.

¹²⁷ See Jan Komárek, "In the Court(s) We Trust?" On the need for hierarchy and differentiation in the preliminary ruling procedure', (2007) 32 *European Law Review* 467-496, 471-472.

¹²⁸ Alexander Somek, 'Unity and Community: A Tale of Two Monsters and One Unanswered Question', in Maduro/Wind, n 2, 249-261, 249. See also Julio Baquero Cruz, 'Joseph Weiler and the Experience of Law', in Maduro/Wind, n 2, 135-148, 139. And the same applies to the author of this article...

¹²⁹ Somek, n 128, 250.

¹³⁰ See e.g. Alexander Somek, *Individualism: An Essay on the Authority of the European Union* (Oxford: OUP 2008).

¹³¹ Phenomenology is concerned with subjective experience – and is therefore not currently very popular in the study of law, which is geared towards more positivistic social science. That is a mistake. For an exploration of EU law in this vein see 'Pathos and Patina: The Failure and Promise of Constitutionalism in the European Imagination' (2003) 9 *European Law Journal* 14-44.

Liberal legalism may persuade many lawyers (as it has done), and some others too. For Weiler (at least the one writing *Transformation*), however, this has never been enough. Hence the turn in the middle of the essay to ‘ideology, ethos and political culture of European integration’, where analysis gives way to an argument about the very nature and purpose of European integration. The realist analysis of politics as power and interests in the EU (the ‘Voice’) is replaced by political moralism or even political theology.¹³² As will be shown, however, it still remains attached to the liberal legalist ideology, which is never fully overcome.

(c) Communitarian utopia

Drawing on Maarti Koskenniemi’s *From Apology to Utopia*,¹³³ Weiler observes that ‘the classical model of international law is a replication at the international level of the liberal theory of the state’,¹³⁴ whereas the state ‘is implicitly treated as the analogue, on the international level, to the individual within a domestic situation’.¹³⁵ For Weiler, ‘[t]he idea of community is thus posited in juxtaposition to the international version of pure liberalism and substitutes a modified communitarian vision’.¹³⁶ Here, Weiler is concerned with two huge conceptual (and practical) leaps at the same time: first, redefining inter-statal relationships, at least among the Member States of the Community, whereby each constituent part pursues simultaneously its own interest *and* the interest of the community, *which is distinct from the former and not only its extension*. This requires no less than a re-definition of the national self.¹³⁷

¹³² I use this term purposively, since to some extent *Transformation* seems to be preoccupied not to use the conceptual categories brought to political sociology by Carl Schmitt. For an explanation why see Joseph Weiler, ‘Epilogue: Europe’s Dark Legacy. Reclaiming Nationalism and Patriotism’ in Christian Joerges and Navraj Singh Ghaleigh (eds), *Darker Legacies of Law in Europe: The Shadow of National Socialism and Fascism over Europe and its Legal Traditions* (Oxford: Hart 2003), 389-402.

¹³³ *From Apology to Utopia: The Structure of International Legal Argument: Reissue with a New Epilogue* (Cambridge: CUP 2005).

¹³⁴ *Transformation*, 2479.

¹³⁵ *Transformation*, 2479.

¹³⁶ *Transformation*, 2480.

¹³⁷ For a remarkable analysis of this process – as it has actually happened, although probably differently from what Weiler envisaged, see Christopher J Bickerton, *European Integration: From Nation-States to Member States* (Oxford: OUP 2012).

At the same time, and much more profoundly, the community vision concerns the interpersonal level. Weiler refers to several provisions of the Treaty that seek to ‘remove nationality and state affiliation of the individual, so divisive in the past, as the principal referent for transnational human intercourse’.¹³⁸ Weiler’s campaign against old nationalism and the nation state is even more pronounced in his warnings against the ascendancy of the unity vision (which materialized with the Union’s attempt to adopt its own formal constitution):

*The potential corrosive effect on the values of the community vision of European integration are self-evident. Nationality as referent for interpersonal relations, and the human alienating effect of us and them are brought back again, simply transferred from their previous intra- Community context to the new inter- Community one. We have made little progress if the us becomes European (instead of German or French or British) and the them becomes those outside the Community or those inside who do not enjoy the privileges of citizenship.*¹³⁹

In essence, what Weiler argues for here is a sort of cosmopolitan citizenship, where in some important sense people can make a community without circumscribing it by borders or exclusion.¹⁴⁰ These, however, may simply be indispensable and no matter how much *Transformation* claims that the Community vision does not involve the negation of the (nation) state, it may be doing precisely that, while it does not (contrary to what *Transformation* seems to believe) substitute its achievements with something else.

The ‘something else’, which is the Community vision of Europe, must not involve the creation of a European super-state or a new European nation and European nationalism: ‘It would be more than ironic if a polity with its political process set up to counter the excesses of statism ended up coming round full circle and transforming itself into a (super)state’.¹⁴¹ The question is, however, whether

¹³⁸ *Transformation*, 2480-81.

¹³⁹ *Transformation*, 2482, emphasis in the original.

¹⁴⁰ For an incisive conceptualisation of this problem, related directly to the discussion here, see Alexander Somek, *The Cosmopolitan Constitution* (Oxford: OUP 2014), Chapter 5.

¹⁴¹ *Transformation*, 2481.

anything like this can ever succeed.¹⁴² No wonder that the major part of Weiler's writing after *Transformation* is devoted to this issue – and still seems to be unresolved.¹⁴³

More importantly, however, contrary to what *Transformation* claims, it remains embedded in 'the international version of pure liberalism', even when putting forward 'a modified communitarian vision' as a model for the EU.¹⁴⁴ International law based on the 'liberal doctrine of politics' is not interested in states' inner impulses, their values, identities or reasons for their actions.¹⁴⁵ Similarly to this, the liberal conception of the self and her autonomy is not concerned with the inner processes and beliefs of individuals. These are part of their private sphere and protected from encroachment by the public sphere, which is meant to provide space for free contracting among individuals, who - viewed from the outside, only have interests that need to be negotiated.¹⁴⁶

Transformation's communitarian vision – although it concerns both states and individuals – is thus not able to see that the state-qua-individual, represented by the government, is in fact only a symbolic representation, which assumes unity when there are in fact conflicts running through it. Such unity, moreover, is only temporary, since it depends on a momentary constellation that gave rise to the expression of the state's will at a given moment (when the government e.g votes for a certain measure, or supports a fundamental change in the Community's structure). Communitarian

¹⁴² See Jan Komárek, 'Rethinking constitutionalism and democracy . . . again?' (2019) 17 *International Journal of Constitutional Law* 992–1005.

¹⁴³ Most tellingly, compare Joseph HH Weiler, 'Europe: The Case Against the Case for Statehood' (1998) 4 *European Law Journal* 43-62, replying to G. Federico Mancini, 'Europe: The Case for Statehood' (1998) 4 *European Law Journal* 29-42, with Joseph Weiler, 'Van Gend en Loos: The individual as subject and object and the dilemma of European legitimacy' (2014) 12 *International Journal of Constitutional Law* 94–103, 102, where Weiler notes: 'There were many, myself included, who shied away from Mancini's remedy, a European state, and shied away from his contention that this remedy was the only one which was available'.

¹⁴⁴ See the text at n 136.

¹⁴⁵ We must make an important terminological note: Koskenniemi's analysis (and my argument here) is based on the history of political liberalism and its doctrine of politics, which also shaped international law. This 'political liberalism' must not be confused with what has become the 'liberal theory of international relations', represented by Anne-Marie Slaughter and in the context of European studies, by Andrew Moravcsik. These are, contrary to what the idea of liberal autonomy and pluralism prescribes (peoples' preferences as given and not to be shaped by public authority) based on an understanding of state preferences as those ensuing from their internal social processes.

¹⁴⁶ For a critical analysis of liberal autonomy as ideology see David Weberman, 'Liberal Democracy, Autonomy, and Ideology Critique' (1997) 23 *Social Theory and Practice* 205-233.

vision cannot account for changes *within* the state and the various conflicts that shape its international policy.¹⁴⁷

Liberalism also assumes equality among individuals within its legal sphere, which means that individuals are equal in law – regardless of their actual social status or wealth.¹⁴⁸ Translated to the doctrine of international law – and EU law as well – states are assumed to be equal and homogeneous. *Transformation* treats all of them as if they were the same, had the same reasons for participating in the integration project and could influence EU policies in the same way. Germany is equal to Greece in this rendering, a picture that may fit legal prescriptions written in the Treaties,¹⁴⁹ but not the actual political practice.¹⁵⁰

Transformation's notion of politics – which is mostly the politics of member state governments vis-à-vis the Community – is based on *interests*. These interests are mostly reduced to each player's desire to keep (or maximize) power in the decisional balance. Politics, which would allow for articulating such interests, is treated as something given, or better put, existing as a matter of course. It is not something that needs to be generated by a complex processes and which is after all a major culturally and historically contingent *achievement* of a successful polity.¹⁵¹

This achievement may be seen in more descriptive, ostensibly neutral terms, such as e.g. the presence of necessary cleavages that generate politics, or a public sphere.¹⁵² More controversially,

¹⁴⁷ On this see also extremely pertinent observations by Bo Stråth, *Europe's Utopias of Peace, 1815, 1919, 1951* (London: Bloomsbury Academic 2016), 1-22.

¹⁴⁸ For a critical account of this liberal construction (represented by Ronald Dworkin) see Colin M. Macleod, *Liberalism, Justice, and Markets: A Critique of Liberal Equality* (Oxford: Clarendon Press 1998).

¹⁴⁹ 'The Union shall respect the equality of Member States before the Treaties' – Article 4(2) TEU.

¹⁵⁰ For a superb analysis of this question see Bickerton, n 137.

¹⁵¹ See especially *Transformation*, 2423-24, 2452-53, 2462-63. Weiler's discussion of the 'Challenges of "democracy" and "legitimacy"' (see the text at n 68) is in line with this observation in that it focuses on democracy 'measured by the closeness, responsiveness, representativeness, and accountability of the governors to the governed' (*Transformation*, 2470). Nothing in this definition refers to the conditions of what makes 'governors' tied to the 'governed', or how the latter can understand themselves as a collective body. On politics (and democratic politics) as an achievement see especially Pierre Rosanvallon, 'Toward a Philosophical History of the Political' in Pierre Rosanvallon (Samuel Moyned and transl), *Democracy Past and Future* (New York: Columbia UP 2006), 59-76.

¹⁵² On these two notions of politics see various contributions in Thomas Risse (ed), *European Public Spheres: Politics Is Back* (Cambridge: CUP 2014).

politics is possible only when exercised in a polity tied together by a common identity or ‘demos’,¹⁵³ and its legitimacy (and durability) derives from some transcendental source – something that reaches beyond its participants’ life horizons.¹⁵⁴

Transformation came about at a moment when these questions only started to be debated by political scientists and within normative political (and democratic) theory dealing with European integration.¹⁵⁵ The point of this and the following Part of this article is therefore not to criticize *Transformation* for its lack of sophistication.¹⁵⁶ That would be an anachronism going directly against the methodological presuppositions of this article. The aim here is different: to highlight the problematic elements that still survive in the constitutional imaginary created by *Transformation*.

5. Ideology critique: Making visible what Transformation conceals

As shown in the previous part, *Transformation* stands on two conflicting constitutional imaginaries. Moreover, each of them is incomplete: the first mostly consists of liberal-legalist *ideology* and does not offer any utopia (unless the rule of law – or more precisely, the rule by the ECJ – is considered one). Such utopia – the Union’s ‘promised land’ is offered by the second, communitarian imaginary. The traditional nation state and international law, which deals with states, are replaced by a system, in which states and people relate in ways that surpass nationality and the nation state. This utopia, however, is tied to the liberal-legalist ideology with its conception of personhood and

¹⁵³ As discussed (but not embraced) by Joseph Weiler, ‘Does Europe Need a Constitution? Demos, Telos and the German Maastricht Decision’ (1995) 1 *European Law Journal* 219-258.

¹⁵⁴ This last condition relates to the schmittian notion of ‘political theology’ – something that the *Transformation*’s afterword from 2017 calls ‘political messianism’. On political theology and the attempts to ground democratic legitimacy on other structures see Carlo Invernizzi Accetti, ‘Can Democracy Emancipate Itself From Political Theology? Habermas and Lefort on the Permanence of the Theologico-Political’ (2010) 17 *Constellations* 254-270.

¹⁵⁵ See Richard Bellamy and Dario Castiglione, ‘Legitimizing the Euro-“polity” and its “Regime”: The Normative Turn in EU Studies’ (2003) 2 *European Journal of Political Theory* 7-34, who note in the massive footnote 1, which lists this literature, that ‘By and large the lawyers promoted this turn, perhaps because law – especially constitutional law – is explicitly a normative order’.

¹⁵⁶ To the contrary, by distinguishing (formal) democratic legitimacy and social (empirical) legitimacy, Weiler was able to challenge the then widespread belief that the democratic deficit rests in the lack of powers of the European Parliament (and be cured by giving more powers to it). See *Transformation*, 2466-2474.

autonomy. It is made plausible only through remaining blind to key issues that would need to be addressed: material inequality – both among the member state and also their citizens, diverse histories and identities. What is offered instead, is a highly-moralizing vision of a redefined national self, which ignores these key issues.

The following two sections can be seen as an attempt at ideology critique – not in the sense that would condemn *Transformation* as ideological (since all social construction of reality is),¹⁵⁷ but rather through revealing what its imaginary keeps from sight, or what gets distorted by it.¹⁵⁸

(a) History as argument

Few people, if any, have ever noted that *Transformation*'s analysis of the integration process starts in 1958. This is remarkable, given that the period between the establishment of the European Coal and Steel Community in 1951 and the European Economic Community (and the Euratom) in 1957 (if one counts when the respective treaties were signed) was characterized by a significant retreat of the high ambitions of supranationalism, symbolized by the complete erasure of the term from the text of the Treaty of Rome. This was done in order not to provoke hostility against the new organisation, or so warned one of the 'Founding Fathers' of the EEC, Paul-Henri Spaak.¹⁵⁹ The same period saw the end of two ambitious integration projects: the European Defence Community and its corollary, European Political Community, which were rejected by the French National Assembly in 1954.¹⁶⁰

At the same time, however, the Schuman Declaration from 1950 is invoked in the second part of the essay, to support the view that the Declaration (and the Treaty of Paris) *despite their economic content, are best seen as a long- term and transformative strategy for peace among the states of western Europe, principally France and Germany. This strategy tried to*

¹⁵⁷ See the text at n 116.

¹⁵⁸ See Balkin, n 116, 1142. On such understanding of ideology critique see Matthias Lievens, 'Ideology critique and the political: Towards a Schmittian perspective on ideology' (2012) 11 *Contemporary Political Theory* 381-396, 394-395.

¹⁵⁹ See Bruno de Witte, 'The EU as an international legal experiment' in JHH Weiler and G de Búrca, *The Worlds of European Constitutionalism* (Cambridge: CUP 2011), 19-56, 25.

¹⁶⁰ On these two projects see Berthold Rittberger "'No integration without representation" European integration, parliamentary democracy, and two forgotten Communities' (2006) 13 *Journal of European Public Policy* 1211-1229.

address the ‘mischief’ embodied in the excesses of the modern nation state and the traditional model of statal intercourse among them that was premised on full ‘sovereignty’, ‘autonomy’, ‘independence’, and a relentless defense and maximization of the national interest.¹⁶¹

This reading of the Schuman Declaration presents one of the foundational myths of European integration: that it was intended, primarily, to address the excesses of the nation state, exemplified by the war that exterminated a large part of Europe’s population, and that it sought to make a clear break with the past.¹⁶²

It is of course a true part of the story, but only a part. It would give quite a different flavour to the project to say that the project was *also* motivated by France’s desire ‘to ensure a reliable supply of high-grade coal from the Ruhr and thus to enhance the efficiency of its armaments industry’,¹⁶³ as the political economist Barry Eichengreen put it. The historian Alan Milward’s assessment of the Monnet Plan – another foundational document from before 1958 is also blunt: ‘Far from being based on a liberal internationalism, the Monnet Plan was based on the crudest possible expression of mercantilist principles. It was aimed at seizing German resources in order to capture German markets’.¹⁶⁴ Examining the true origins of the European Communities could therefore reveal that the motivations to establish the close economic cooperation between France and Germany were rather afar from those presented in *Transformation*.

Second, seen from Africa, the Treaty of Rome looked like an attempt by the declining colonial empires of Europe to maintain their control over ‘their’ territories.¹⁶⁵ For Kwame Nkrumah, the first prime minister of Ghana, the Treaty ‘mark[ed] the advent of neo-colonialism in Africa’.¹⁶⁶

Transformation only glosses over this issue in the second afterword, firstly published in 2012: ‘Some old habits, such as the White Man’s Burden and the missionary tradition, die hard’, when

¹⁶¹ *Transformation*, 2478, emphasis in the original.

¹⁶² On a critique of such reading of the Declaration see e.g. Antonin Cohen, ‘Why call it a “European Community”?’ Ideological Continuities and Institutional Design of Nascent European Organisations’ (2018) 27 *Contemporary European History* 326-344.

¹⁶³ Barry Eichengreen, *The European economy since 1945: Coordinated capitalism and beyond* (Princeton, Princeton UP 2007), 167.

¹⁶⁴ Alan S. Milward, *The Reconstruction of Western Europe 1945–51* (London: Routledge 2005 [1984]), 104.

¹⁶⁵ Peo Hansen and Stefan Jonsson, *Eurafrica: The Untold History of European Integration and Colonialism* (London: Bloomsbury Academic 2014), 270.

¹⁶⁶ *Ibid*, quoting ‘Address to the Ghana National Assembly’, 30 May 1961.

quoting from the Schuman Declaration the following sentence: ‘With increased resources Europe will be able to pursue the achievement of one of its essential tasks, namely, the development of the African continent’.¹⁶⁷

An additional piece of the geopolitical context was the role of the United States of America, with its desire to make Europe (or better put, France and Germany) ready to stand on its side in an expected conflict with the Soviet Union and its satellites.¹⁶⁸ The United States’ intention was, ‘through furthering the process of economic recovery in Western Europe, to develop a bloc of states which would share similar political, social, economic and cultural values to those which the United States itself publicly valued and claimed to uphold’.¹⁶⁹ In *Transformation*’s narrative, the United States does not however play an important role at all (except for its constitutional imaginary, noted above). The key moment seems to be the one of European ‘founding fathers’ *self-reflection*, not their *acceptance* of ideas coming from outside.¹⁷⁰

Finally, given that *Transformation* was published in 1991, the absence of 1989 – the fall of the Iron Curtain and the momentum this provided for the transformation (with a small “t”) of Europe, is also remarkable. It may be due to the reluctance of the then 12 member states to conceive the enlargement of the Community to the ‘Other Europe’, well-documented by an early comment on

¹⁶⁷ Joseph H H Weiler, ‘*The Transformation of Europe Revisited: The Things that Do Not Transform*’, in Maduro/Wind, n 2, 333-351, 347.

¹⁶⁸ See Mark Gilbert, ‘Partners and Rivals: Assessing the American Role’ in Wolfram Kaiser and Antonio Varsori (eds), *European Union History: Themes and Debates* (London: Palgrave Macmillan 2010), 169-189, 171-177.

¹⁶⁹ Milward, n 164, 94. Milward at 95 however adds the following qualification:

About so complex and varied a set of politico-economic relationships it seems vain to generalize. Yet it can certainly be said that the idea that the United States sought no extra political or economic gain in return for Marshall Aid is nonsense, that the idea that the gains achieved were so large as to have shaped the politico-economic future of Western Europe is nonsense also, that the gains made by the United States can only be judged in relation to specific issues and specific countries, and that the limitations to the exercise of American power and influence through the [European Recovery Programme] were subtle, complicated, but always present and often narrow. In the end it is, at least as far as Western Europe is concerned, for the story might be very different in Greece, those limitations that are the most striking aspect of the story.

¹⁷⁰ In this relation it is interesting to note that the word ‘integration’ was promoted by the US chief of the European Economic Co-operation Administration, Paul Hoffman. See Stråth, n 147, 354.

Transformation, published in the same issue of the *Yale Law Journal*.¹⁷¹ But the absence of it in the later afterwords only reinforces the impression: that member states and even the idea of Europe remain a rather abstract idea, uprooted from their geopolitical and historical context.

Based on the foregoing observations, one could conclude that *Transformation* is based on bad history, or that European post-war history got misused in its narrative. That would however miss the point. As argued above, *Transformation* is piece written by a lawyer for lawyers. Lawyers do not study history: they use it as argument. Put most bluntly by a prominent legal historian from the United States, this would be ‘judging as history a use of the past that is not history but advocacy’.¹⁷² He continues: ‘The purpose of the advocate, unlike that of the historian, is to use the past for the elucidation of the present, to solve some contemporary problem or, most often, to carry an argument. It is the past put in the service of winning the case at bar’.¹⁷³ Here the (selective rendering) of Europe’s past is put in the service of its successful transformation. For this to succeed, however, at least one more step is needed: one must ignore the political-economic dimension behind it.

(b) The neglect of political economy

There is one more profound element of *Transformation*’s version of European integration history. By rendering its origins in the post-war context, it makes it almost natural to see the primary motivation to pursue integration as the need ‘to address the ‘mischief’ embodied in the excesses of the modern nation state’¹⁷⁴ or even to see it ‘as the beginning of a process that would bring about [its] elimination’.¹⁷⁵ It is however important not to lose sight of a longer-term perspective. Before “excessive nationalism”, there was the Great Depression and the crisis of inter-war capitalism,

¹⁷¹ Romana Sadurska, ‘Reshaping Europe. Or “How to Keep Poor Cousins in (Their) Home”’: A Comment on *The Transformation of Europe*’ (1991) 100 *Yale Law Journal* 2501-2510.

¹⁷² John Phillip Reid, ‘The Jurisprudence of Liberty: The Ancient Constitution in the Legal Historiography of the Seventeenth and Eighteenth Centuries’ in Ellis Sandoz (ed), *The Roots of Liberty: Magna Carta, Ancient Constitution, and the Anglo-American Tradition of Rule of Law* (Indianapolis: Liberty Fund 1993), 214.

¹⁷³ *Ibid*, 215.

¹⁷⁴ *Transformation*, 2478.

¹⁷⁵ *Ibid*.

which gave rise to fascism and national socialism.¹⁷⁶ Karl Polanyi has described this process in his *Great Transformation* published in 1944.¹⁷⁷ It echoed arguments made in the Weimar context by the social democrat – and prominent constitutional theorist Hermann Heller, who took the view (already in 1928!) that ‘conditions of extreme socioeconomic inequality were incompatible with the survival of a constitutional democracy, because democracy requires a certain degree of social homogeneity, or at least the prospect of such, to sustain political legitimacy’.¹⁷⁸

The post-war elites however took lessons from another German liberal thinker, Karl Loewenstein and his argument for ‘militant democracy’. As Michael Wilkinson puts it, ‘In constitutional enquiry, the focus undoubtedly was on the dangers of strong (unfettered) democracy, rather than, as Heller and Polanyi had warned, of unfettered capitalism and its tendency towards socio-economic inequality’.¹⁷⁹ *Transformation*’s history of European integration is put firmly in this liberal tradition, repressing the memory of the Great Depression by that of the War. It confirms an avoidance of substantive questions of political economy, typical for most writing set in the constitutional imaginary established by *Transformation*.

This observation opens up the whole set of issues that cannot be addressed here; it relates to the general neglect of political economy in the mainstream legal thinking of the West, which dates back to the post-war era and which has only recently – in the wake of the global financial crisis of 2008-, started to change.¹⁸⁰

¹⁷⁶ See Michael Wilkinson, ‘Authoritarian Liberalism: The Conjuncture Behind the Crisis’ *LSE Legal Studies Working Paper* No. 5/2018, available at <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3137329>.

¹⁷⁷ Karl Polanyi, *The Great Transformation: The Political and Economic Origins of Our Time* (Boston: Beacon Press 1957 [1944]), 71. For a summary of Polanyi’s analysis see Martin Höpner and Armin Schäfer, ‘Embeddedness and Regional Integration: Waiting for Polanyi in a Hayekian Setting’ (2012) 66 *International Organization* 429-455, 432-434.

¹⁷⁸ Wilkinson, n 176, 13.

¹⁷⁹ *Ibid*, 14. See also Stråth, n 147, 361.

¹⁸⁰ See particularly Michael Wilkinson’s numerous publications, e.g. ‘The Specter of Authoritarian Liberalism: Reflections on the Constitutional Crisis of the European Union’ (2013) 14 *German Law Journal* 527-560; ‘Authoritarian Liberalism in the European Constitutional Imagination: Second Time as Farce?’ (2015) 21 *European Law Journal* 313-339 and ‘The Reconstitution of Postwar Europe: Liberal Excesses, Democratic Deficiencies’ in M. Dowdle and M. Wilkinson (eds.) *Constitutionalism Beyond Liberalism* (Cambridge: CUP 2017) 38-79.

6. Conclusion: So, why read it today?

The short answer is: because *Transformation*'s imaginary and central ideas remain influential, without much reflection provided on the contradictions between liberal ideology and communitarian utopia. Moreover, the ideological effects of *Transformation*'s imaginary make us blind to issues that cry out for articulation. Only if we see through these contradictions and identify *Transformation*'s 'blind spots' can we begin to think of a different imaginary that may keep the European integration process going – although this does not necessarily mean that it becomes deeper or wider. This imaginary will have to be different the the liberal-legalist one, which still informs much thinking about a new order that will come 'at the end of globalization'.¹⁸¹

Several incidents – events of the ongoing crisis of the EU – illustrate this need.

The first is the crisis of authority in the EU and the increasing number of challenges to the ECJ's prerogative to have the final say on the questions of constitutionality in the EU. In reaction to the ruling of the German Federal Constitutional Court,¹⁸² which declared the ECJ's judgment in *Wiess* ultra vires,¹⁸³ a group of European academics composed a 'joint statement' condemning the German court and calling on the Commission to initiate infringement proceedings against Germany.¹⁸⁴

There is no reflection on how such a legalistic approach may ever save the authority of the ECJ (and EU law), rather than escalating conflict further.¹⁸⁵ The proposal on creating a special chamber of the ECJ, where European judges would sit together with their colleagues from national constitutional courts fares only slightly better,¹⁸⁶ as it assumes that the constitutional conflict in the EU can be solved in a legal way, by a judicial institution.

¹⁸¹ Stephen D. King, *Grawe New World: The End of Globalization, the Return of History* (New Haven: Yale UP 2017).

¹⁸² BVerfG, judgment of the Second Senate of 5 May 2020, 2 BvR 859/15, paras. 1-237, http://www.bverfg.de/e/rs20200505_2bvr085915en.html.

¹⁸³ ECJ (Grand Chamber), judgment of 11 December 2018, *Weiss and Others*, C-493/17, EU:C:2018:1000.

¹⁸⁴ See Kelemen et al, n 11.

¹⁸⁵ For a much more reflexive contribution to the debate, which argued for the initiation of the infringement procedure see Daniel Sarmiento, 'An Infringement Action against Germany after its Constitutional Court's ruling in Weiss? The Long Term and the Short Term' *EU Law Live* 12 May 2020, <https://eulawlive.com/op-ed-an-infringement-action-against-germany-after-its-constitutional-courts-ruling-in-weiss-the-long-term-and-the-short-term-by-daniel-sarmiento/>

¹⁸⁶ Joseph HH Weiler and Daniel Sarmiento, 'The EU Judiciary After Weiss – Proposing A New Mixed Chamber of the Court of Justice' *EU Law Live* 1 June 2020, <https://eulawlive.com/op-ed-the-eu-judiciary-after-weiss-proposing-a-new->

The trust in courts to solve complex social problems, in other words, liberal legalism,¹⁸⁷ also informs some responses to the ‘rule of law crisis’, as the turn to illiberal authoritarianism gets often called.¹⁸⁸ The crisis gave rise to a number of rulings by the ECJ, which have further shifted the balance of competences towards the Court.¹⁸⁹ For some people ‘these decisions amount to a veritable stepping stone towards a “Union of values” and stand on a par with the Court’s constitutionalizing jurisprudence in *van Gend en Loos* and *Costa/ENEL*’.¹⁹⁰ However, once again, this puts so much burden on law and legal institutions that may not be able to bear it. Finally, the exalted moralism adopted by some actors in the course of the economic,¹⁹¹ and migration crisis,¹⁹² simply overlooks the complex and complicated histories of the states that came to form the Union as it exists today. An imaginary of ‘peace and prosperity’ is not enough (if it ever was) to justify – and make *invisible* - the various dimensions of domination within Europe, especially if prosperity is given only to some, while others enjoy its opposite side: austerity. The ‘old’ way of organising relationships between individuals and their collectives: citizenship, statehood, social or welfare state based on bounded, not cosmopolitan solidarity may seem to be lost. However, before we condemn them to the dustbin of history, we should seriously examine whether the alternatives are (not) such as to cover new forms of injustice and domination. Reading *Transform*

[mixed-chamber-of-the-court-of-justice-by-daniel-sarmiento-and-j-h-h-weiler/](#). The same idea was proposed by Weiler, together with Ulrich Haltern and Franz Mayer in ‘European Democracy and its Critique: Five Uneasy Pieces’ *EUI Working Paper RSC* No. 95/11, <https://cadmus.eui.eu/handle/1814/1386> at 46.

¹⁸⁷ See the text at n 93.

¹⁸⁸ For critical comments on this crisis see Jan-Werner Müller, ‘Reflections on Europe’s “Rule of Law Crises”’ in Poul F. Kjaer and Niklas Olsen (eds), *Critical Theories of Crisis in Europe: From Weimar to the Euro* (London: Rowman & Littlefield 2016), 161-175.

¹⁸⁹ See Bogdandy, n 10, 712.

¹⁹⁰ Bogdandy, n 10, 712-713.

¹⁹¹ See Marion Fourcade, Philippe Steiner, Wolfgang Streeck and Cornelia Woll, ‘Moral categories in the financial crisis’ (2013) 11 *Socio-Economic Review* 601-627.

¹⁹² See e.g. Jan T. Gross, ‘Eastern Europe’s Crisis of Shame’, *Project Syndicate* 13 September 2015, <https://www.project-syndicate.org/commentary/eastern-europe-refugee-crisis-xenophobia-by-jan-gross-2015-09>, who said that in the course of the migration crisis (summer 2015) ‘Eastern Europeans have revealed themselves to be intolerant, illiberal, xenophobic, and incapable of remembering the spirit of solidarity that carried them to freedom a quarter-century ago’.

Author: Jan Komárek

Title: Why read The Transformation of Europe today? On the limits of a liberal constitutional imaginary

iCourts Working Paper Series, No. 213, 2020

Publication date: 2/September/2020

URL: <http://jura.ku.dk/icourts/working-papers/>

© Author

iCourts Working Paper Series

ISSN: 2246-4891

Jan Komárek, Professor of European law, *iCourts*, Faculty of Law, University of Copenhagen

Email: Jan.Komarek@jur.ku.dk

The iCourts Online Working Paper Series publishes pre-print manuscripts on international courts, their role in a globalising legal order, and their impact on politics and society and takes an explicit interdisciplinary perspective.

Papers are available at <http://jura.ku.dk/icourts/>

iCourts

- The Danish National Research Foundation's Centre of Excellence for International Courts

The Faculty of Law

University of Copenhagen

Karen Blixens Plads 16

2300 Copenhagen S

E-mail: icourts@jur.ku.dk
Tel. +45 35 32 26 26